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APPLIED LINEAR ALGEBRA 2025
in honor of Zhong-Zhi Bai

TIMETABLE AND
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

July 3-5, 2025
Novi Sad, Serbia

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Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad

Faculty of Technical Sciences,
University of Novi Sad

Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts,
Branch in Novi Sad

ALA Group, Novi Sad

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TIMETABLE

	WEDNESDAY (July 2)	THURSDAY (July 3)	FRIDAY (July 4)	SATURDAY (July 5)
9:00 - 9:30	Registration	Registration	James Nagy	Parallel sessions 4
9:30 - 10:00		Opening	Kang-Ya Lu	coffee break
10:00 - 10:30		Zhong-Zhi Bai	coffee break	Parallel sessions 1
10:30 - 11:00		coffee break	Parallel sessions 1	Parallel sessions 5
11:00 - 11:30		Chen Greif		
11:30 - 12:00				
12:00 - 12:30				
12:30 - 13:00				
13:00 - 15:00		lunch	lunch	lunch
15:00 - 15:30	Registration	Massimiliano Pontil	Parallel sessions 2	Parallel sessions 6
15:30 - 16:00		Michelle Parrinello	coffee break	
16:00-16:30		coffee break	Parallel sessions 3	
16:30 - 17:00		Yuji Nakatsukasa		
17:00 - 17:30				
17:30 - 18:00				
18:00 - 18:30				
18:30 - 19:00				
19:00 - 19:30				
19:30 -				GALA dinner

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PLENARY LECTURES TIMETABLE

Thursday, July 3rd

chair: Stevan Pilipović

10:30 - 11:30 Zhong-Zhi Bai

Admissibly Randomized Coordinate Descent Methods for Computing Extreme Eigenpairs of Symmetric Matrices

12:00 - 13:00 Chen Greif

Numerical Solution of Double Saddle-Point Systems

chair: Vladimir Kostić

15:00 - 16:00 Massimiliano Pontil

Linear Operators Learning for Dynamical Systems

16:00 - 17:00 Michelle Parrinello

Molecular dynamics: the AI revolution

17:30 - 18:30 Yuji Nakatsukasa

Randomized algorithms in numerical linear algebra and the column subset selection problem

Friday, July 4th

chair: Teodor Atanacković

9:00 - 10:00 James Nagy

Mixed Precision Arithmetic for Large Scale Inverse Problems

10:00 - 11:00 Kang-Ya Lu

Multigrid Method with Greedy Partial Block-Jacobi Smoother for Solving Two-Dimensional Anomalous Diffusion Equations

* Machine Learning and Numerical Computations Workshop

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PARALLEL SESSIONS TIMETABLE

Friday, July 4th	
Parallel sessions 1	
chair: Marko Petković	
11:30 - 12:00	Lu Wang
12:00 - 12:30	Wen-Ting Wu
12:30 - 13:00	Liu Hao
chair: Massimiliano Pontil	
11:30 - 12:00	Yury Gryazhin
12:00 - 12:30	Arghya Sinha
12:30 - 13:00	Vladimir Bapic
	* Parallel Compact PFFT-Type Algorithms in the Machine Learning Kernel Methods for 3D Scattering Problems
	* On the convergence of denoiser-driven image reconstruction
	* Joint Communication, Localization, Sensing, and Radio SLAM
Parallel sessions 2	
chair: James Nagy	
15:00 - 15:30	AI-Li Yang
15:30 - 16:00	Suzana Miodragović
16:00 - 16:30	Stanislav Morozov
chair: Pietro Novelli	
15:00 - 15:30	Qian Zuo
15:30 - 16:00	Zhengda Huang
16:00 - 16:30	Rui Li
	* K-means clustering based maximal residual Kaczmarz methods for solving large scale system of linear equations
	* The tan Θ theorems for definite matrix pairs
	* Alternating minimization method for low-rank approximation of matrices and tensors in the Chebyshev norm
	* Accelerated multiple row- and column-action methods and their convergence analyses
	* On A Deterministic Block Newton-Kaczmarz Method
	* Greedy Block Extended Kaczmarz Method for Solving the Least Squares Problems
Parallel sessions 3	
chair: Chen Greif	
17:00 - 17:30	Rachel Yovel
17:30 - 18:00	Sean Y Hon
18:00 - 18:30	Kim Taehyeong
chair: Karim Lounici	
17:00 - 17:30	Pietro Novelli
17:30 - 18:00	Matia Bojović
18:00 - 18:30	Marko Petković
	* Numerical Linear algebra for Operator Learning: Challenges and Opportunities
	* Convex Extension of the Kaczmarz Algorithm for Efficient Computation of Sparse Inverses of Positive Definite Matrices
	* Neural dynamics methods for solving system of matrix equations and applications to advanced data analytics

* Machine Learning and Numerical Computations Workshop

Applied Linear Algebra (ALA) 2025

in honor of Zhong-Zhi Bai

PARALLEL SESSIONS TIMETABLE

Saturday, July 5th	
Parallel sessions 4	
chair: Dodig Marija	
9:00 - 9:30 Mehdi Najafi Kalyani	Componentwise accuracy in multilinear PageRank problems
9:30 - 10:00 Ani Velo	Markov and Signed Markov Matrices for Impact Problems in Layered Elastic Media
10:00 - 10:30 Piotr Mackowiak	Explicit form of J.C.P. Miller formula and some applications
chair: Kang-Ya Lu	
9:00 - 9:30 Abdellatif Mouhssine	A New Combination of Vector Extrapolation Methods and Multigrid Solvers For Isogeometric Analysis Applied To Linear and Nonlinear Problems
9:30 - 10:00 Marko Stošić	Projection on the intersection of convex sets
10:00 - 10:30 Marija Dodig	Direct link between bounded rank-perturbation problem and matrix pencil completion problem
10:30 - 11:00 Marija Mилоша-Pandur	\mathfrak{D} -subspace algorithms for detecting large definite matrix pairs
Parallel sessions 5	
chair: Ninošlav Truhar	
11:30 - 12:00 Ivana Kurmanović Vrić	Stability and Perturbation Bounds for Gyroscopic Systems
12:00 - 12:30 Michal Habera	Numerically stable evaluation of closed-form expressions for eigenvalues of 3×3 matrices
12:30 - 13:00 Fotis Babouklis	Improving bounds for eigenvalues
chair: Rui Li	
11:30 - 12:00 Achya Dax	A restarted Krylov method for small eigenvalues
12:00 - 12:30 Malena Sabate Landman	Recent advances on inner-product free Krylov methods
12:30 - 13:00 Erna Kovač Begović	Randomized algorithms for coupled decompositions
Parallel sessions 6	
chair: Suzana Miodragović	
15:00 - 15:30 Ninošlav Truhar	Damping optimization of mechanical systems – rod/string model
15:30 - 16:00 João Cardoso	Solving a Class of Fractional Differential Equation Using the Matrix Mittag-Leffler Function
16:00 - 16:30 Jelena Tomanić	Quadratures with quasi-degree of exactness
chair: Marko Stošić	
15:00 - 15:30 Ana Perović	Trace maximization algorithm for the approximate tensor diagonalization
15:30 - 16:00 Susana López Moreno	Tensor Means under Tensor-Tensor Products with Invertible Linear Transforms
16:00 - 16:30 Thomas Karam	Perfect properties of the ranks of some tensors

Honorary lecture

Admissibly Randomized Coordinate Descent Methods for Computing Extreme Eigenpairs of Symmetric Matrices

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For solving symmetric eigenvalue problems of extremely large matrices that cannot be stored in a whole in the computer memory, we propose a class of admissibly randomized coordinate descent methods by minimizing the corresponding Rayleigh quotients. These iteration methods only call of and operate on a column of the matrix at each of their iteration steps, so they require a small computer memory and have a small computational complexity. We analyze the convergence property of these admissibly randomized coordinate descent methods, and confirm their implemental effectiveness by numerical experiments.

Plenary lectures

Numerical Solution of Double Saddle-Point Systems

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Double saddle-point systems have been drawing increasing attention in the past few years, due to the importance of multiphysics problems and the challenge in developing efficient numerical solvers. In this talk I describe some of their numerical properties and make distinctions between this family and standard saddle-point systems. We derive eigenvalue bounds on the eigenvalues of preconditioned matrices based on block diagonal preconditioners using Schur complements, and it is shown that the eigenvalues are clustered within a few intervals bounded away from zero, giving rise to rapid convergence of minimum residual Krylov subspace solvers. Analysis and numerical experiments on relevant examples, such as the Stokes-Darcy equations, illustrate our findings.

Mixed Precision Arithmetic for Large Scale Inverse Problems

James Nagy and Luke Onisk

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In recent years a substantial amount of work has been done on developing mixed-precision algorithms for linear systems, methods that can exploit capabilities of modern GPU architectures. However, very little work has been done for ill-conditioned problems that arise from large-scale inverse problems. Special considerations, which normally do not arise when solving well-conditioned problems, such as incorporating regularization into the developed methods, need to be considered. In this talk we consider iterative refinement methods for least squares problems, and show the connection to iterated Tikhonov regularization and the preconditioned Landweber method.

Multigrid Method with Greedy Partial Block Jacobi Smoother for Solving Two-Dimensional Anomalous Diffusion Equations

Kang-Ya Lu and Xiao-Yun Zhang

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Based on the block Jacobi splitting, a kind of *greedy partial block Jacobi* (GPBJ) iteration method is constructed by greedily selecting the blocks with relatively large residuals and performing the block Jacobi iteration on the selected blocks. Theoretical analysis demonstrates that the GPBJ iteration is unconditionally convergent if the coefficient matrix of the linear system is H -matrix. Then combining with the alternating direction strategy, the GPBJ smoothed multigrid method is designed to solve the discrete linear system of two-dimensional anomalous diffusion equations, where the coefficient matrix is strictly diagonally dominant. Numerical experiments indicate that the multigrid method smoothed by the GPBJ iteration can significantly reduce the computation time for solving the considered discrete linear system.

References:

- [1] Bai, Z.-Z., Wu, W.-T.: On greedy randomized Kaczmarz method for solving large sparse linear systems, *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 40(2018) A592-A606.
- [2] Frommer, A., Szyld, D.B.: On the convergence of randomized and greedy relaxation schemes for solving nonsingular linear systems of equations, *Numer. Algorithms*, 92(2023) 639-664.
- [3] Lin, X.-L., Ng, M.K., Sun, H.-W.: A multigrid method for linear systems arising from time-dependent two-dimensional space-fractional diffusion equations, *J. Comput. Phys.*, 336(2017) 69-86.

Contributed talks

On convergence rate of the randomized multiplicative Schwarz method

Lu Wang

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The randomized coordinate descent (RCD) method and the randomized Kaczmarz (RK) method are two classical and widely-used randomized iteration methods for solving large-scale linear systems, they can be regarded as two special cases of the randomized multiplicative Schwarz (RMS) method. Motivated by the exact error analysis of the RCD method and the RK method, we conduct a closed-form formula for the solution error of the RMS method and further give a tighter upper bound for its convergence rate. On this basis, we unify the convergence results of the RCD method and the RK method, and generalize them to the more general extrapolated RCD method and extrapolated RK method. Numerical experiments confirm that the new estimate for the convergence rate of the RMS method is more accurate, and it can help us to find a more proper relaxation parameter.

References:

- [1] Griebel, M., Oswald, P.: Greedy and randomized versions of the multiplicative Schwarz method, *Linear Algebra Appl.* 437 (2012) 1596-1610.
- [2] Bai, Z.-Z., Wu, W.-T.: On convergence rate of the randomized Kaczmarz method, *Linear Algebra Appl.* 553 (2018) 252-269.
- [3] Bai, Z.-Z., Wang, L., Wu, W.-T.: On convergence rate of the randomized Gauss-Seidel method, *Linear Algebra Appl.* 611 (2021) 237-252.

The two-subspace randomized extended Kaczmarz method for large linear systems

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The randomized Kaczmarz method is an efficient row-action iteration solver for solving the very large systems of linear equations. Due to its simplicity, it has been widely used in the areas of computerized tomography, signal processing and image reconstruction, machine learning and so on. The randomized extended Kaczmarz method extends the randomized Kaczmarz method to solve the inconsistent linear systems. In this talk, based on a generalization of the two-subspace randomized Kaczmarz method without the assumptions of unit row norms and full column rank on the coefficient matrix, we propose a block version of the randomized extended Kaczmarz method for solving the large-scale linear least-squares problem, called the two-subspace randomized extended Kaczmarz method. This block method does not require any row or column pivoting. Theoretical analysis and numerical results show that this method is much more efficient than the randomized extended Kaczmarz method in some cases. When the coefficient matrix is of full column rank, it can also outperform the randomized coordinate descent method.

References:

- [1] Bai, Z.-Z., Wu, W.-T.: Randomized Kaczmarz iteration methods: Algorithmic extensions and convergence theory, *Jpn. J. Ind. Appl. Math.* 40 (2023) 1421-1443.
- [2] Wu, W.-T.: On two-subspace randomized extended Kaczmarz method for solving large linear least-squares problems, *Numer. Algorithms* 89 (2022) 1-31.

The Maximum Residual Block Kaczmarz Algorithm Based on Feature Selection

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Based on K-means method, an effective block-row partitions algorithm was proposed, which involves partitioning the rows of the coefficient matrix $A \in \mathbf{R}^{m \times n}$. However, with the increase of the size of the coefficient matrix, the time required for the partitioning process will increase significantly. To address this problem, we consider selecting features from the columns of the matrix A to obtain a low-rank matrix $\tilde{A} \in \mathbf{R}^{m \times d}$, ($d \ll n$). Lasso is a regression analysis method for feature selection, which is simple and has excellent processing ability for high-dimensional data. In view of this, we first introduce a new criterion for selecting the projection block, and propose the maximum residual block Kaczmarz algorithm. Then, we put forward the feature selection algorithm based on Lasso, and further present a maximum residual block Kaczmarz algorithm based on feature selection. We analyze the convergence of these algorithms and demonstrate their effectiveness through numerical results, while also verifying the performance of the proposed algorithms in image reconstruction.

References:

- [1] Bai, Z.-Z. : Parallel matrix multisplitting block relaxation iteration methods, *Math. Numer. Sinica* 17 (1995) 238-252. (In Chinese)
- [2] Berman, A., Plemmons, R.J. : *Nonnegative Matrices in the Mathematical Sciences*, *Classics in Applied Mathematics*, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (SIAM), Philadelphia, 1994.

The $\tan \Theta$ theorems for definite matrix pairs

Suzana Miodragović, Ivana Kuzmanović Ivičić, Matea Ugrica Vukojević and
Ninoslav Truhar

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In this talk, we will discuss the perturbation of a Hermitian matrix pair (H, M) , where H is non-singular and M is a positive definite matrix. The corresponding perturbed pair $(\tilde{H}, \tilde{M}) = (H + \delta H, M + \delta M)$ is assumed to satisfy the conditions that \tilde{H} remains non-singular and \tilde{M} remains positive definite. We derive an upper bound for the tangent of the angles between the eigenspaces of the perturbed and unperturbed pairs. The rotation of the eigenspaces due to perturbation is measured in a matrix-dependent scalar product.

We will demonstrate that the absolute and relative $\tan \Theta$ bounds for the standard eigenvalue problem are special cases of our newly derived bounds. Additionally, we will show how this bound can be applied to stable gyroscopic systems.

References:

- [1] Kuzmanović Ivičić, I., Miodragović, S., Ugrica, M.: The $\tan \Theta$ theorem for definite matrix pairs, *Linear and multilinear algebra* 70 (2022), 1-17.
- [2] Miodragović, S., Truhar, N., Kuzmanović Ivičić, I.: Relative perturbation $\tan \Theta$ theorems for definite matrix pairs, *Electronic Transactions on Numerical Analysis* 60 (2024), 364-380.
- [3] Kuzmanović Ivičić, I., Miodragović, S.: Perturbation bounds for stable gyroscopic systems, *BIT Numerical Mathematics* 63/1 (2023), 1-16.

Alternating minimization method for low-rank approximation of matrices and tensors in the Chebyshev norm

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The problem of a low-rank approximation is ubiquitous in science. Traditionally, this problem is solved in unitary invariant norms such as Frobenius or the spectral norm due to the existence of efficient methods for building approximations. The quality of the approximation for the unitary invariant norms is related to the decay rate of singular values. However, recent results reveal the potential for low-rank approximations in the Chebyshev norm, which naturally arises in many applications. It can be shown that many matrices with a slow decay rate of singular values admit a low-rank approximation in the Chebyshev norm. We propose the alternating minimization method for constructing low-rank approximations of matrices and tensors in the canonical polyadic format in the Chebyshev norm. To this end, we discuss the problem of the best uniform approximation of vector by a given linear subspace, which is of independent interest. The final algorithm is capable of constructing low-rank approximations for matrices of sizes up to tens of thousands of rows and columns in a feasible time and outperforms the other methods in approximation quality. We also analyze the proposed algorithm and show that it can be used to construct optimal rank-1 approximations.

References:

- [1] Morozov, S., Zheltkov, D., Osinsky, A.: Accelerated alternating minimization algorithm for low-rank approximations in the Chebyshev norm (2024) arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.05247.

Numerical solvers for the Helmholtz equations: preconditioning approaches featuring multigrid methods and saddle-point systems

Rachel Yovel and Eran Treister

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In this talk we present a novel block-preconditioner for the elastic Helmholtz equation, based on a reduction to acoustic Helmholtz equations. Both versions of the Helmholtz equations are challenging numerically. The elastic Helmholtz equation is larger, as a system of PDEs, and harder to solve due to its more complicated physics. It was recently suggested that the elastic Helmholtz equation can be reformulated as a generalized saddle-point system, opening the door to the current development. Utilizing the approximate commutativity of the underlying differential operators, we suggest a block-triangular preconditioner whose diagonal blocks are acoustic Helmholtz operators. Thus, we enable the solution of the elastic version using virtually any existing solver for the acoustic version as a black-box. We prove a sufficient condition for the convergence of our method, that sheds light on the long questioned role of the commutator in the convergence of approximate commutator preconditioners. We show scalability of our preconditioner with respect to the Poisson ratio and with respect to the grid size. We compare our approach, combined with multigrid solve of each block, to a recent monolithic multigrid method for the elastic Helmholtz equation. The block-acoustic multigrid achieves a lower computational cost for various heterogeneous media, and a significantly lower memory consumption, compared to the monolithic approach. It results in a fast solution method for wave propagation problems in challenging heterogeneous media in 2D and 3D.

An optimal parallel-in-time preconditioner for parabolic optimal control problems

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In this talk, we propose a novel diagonalization-based preconditioner for the all-at-once linear system arising from the optimal control problem of parabolic equations. The proposed preconditioner is constructed using an ϵ -circulant modification of the rotated block diagonal preconditioning technique [1], which can be efficiently diagonalized via fast Fourier transforms in a parallel-in-time fashion. When the generalized minimal residual method is applied to the preconditioned system, we demonstrate that, with an appropriate choice of ϵ , the convergence rate achieves linearity, independent of the matrix size and the regularization parameter.

References:

- [1] Bai, Z-Z., Lu, K-Y.: Optimal rotated block-diagonal pre-conditioning for discretized optimal control problems constrained with fractional time-dependent diffusive equations, *Applied Numerical Mathematics* (2021), 163:126-146.

Continuous piecewise regression with 1-Wasserstein distance regularization

Taehyeong Kim¹ and Hayoung Choi^{1,2}

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In this study, we present an optimization-driven framework for determining the optimal number of breakpoints in continuous piecewise polynomial regression, addressing the shortcomings of subjective and heuristic methods. By adding the 1-Wasserstein distance between residual distributions as a regularization term, we reformulate breakpoint selection as a structured optimization problem with theoretical guarantees. Under the assumption of independent and identically distributed Gaussian noise, we prove that minimizing the average pairwise Wasserstein distance of residuals effectively identifies true breakpoints. We also propose algorithms to solve the optimization problem. Numerical experiments on synthetic datasets validate the robustness and accuracy of the proposed method. The application of Mauna Loa atmospheric data reveals a distinct acceleration in atmospheric carbon dioxide growth, demonstrating its utility to uncover trends in complex real-world systems.

References:

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Componentwise accuracy in multilinear PageRank problems

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We consider the multilinear PageRank [3], problem, i.e., finding a stochastic vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$ such that $\mathbf{x} = (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{v} + \alpha P(\mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{x})$, where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, \mathbf{v} is stochastic ($\mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{v} = 1$) and $P \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n \times n^2}$ is column-stochastic ($\mathbf{1}^T P = \mathbf{1}^T$).

We study the behavior of the solution under componentwise perturbations, i.e., under the distance $d(\tilde{x}, x) = \max_i |x_i - \tilde{x}_i|/|x_i|$. This perturbation model is natural in certain probability applications where accuracy is required also on very small entries of the solution.

An important case in the equation is $\alpha \approx 0.5$, since for $\alpha = 0.5$ the system is degenerate because two continuous branches of solutions meet.

We prove a componentwise perturbation bound, following a strategy that had been used for [1]. This first bound is however suboptimal, since it shows that the condition number of the problem under componentwise perturbations diverges to infinity for $\alpha \rightarrow 0.5$. We show that the bound can be improved by restricting to perturbations that preserve the constraint $\mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{v} = 1$ and $\mathbf{1}^T P = \mathbf{1}^T$, leading to a bound that does not diverge and reflects the numerical behavior.

One important theoretical tool in the proof is a certain generalized inverse of an M-matrix. We discuss computational issues relative to its computation.

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Markov and Signed Markov Matrices for Impact Problems in Layered Elastic Media

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In this presentation, we establish necessary and sufficient conditions to detect and construct Markov/probability matrices of any size in the context of a discrete model for the stress wave propagation in impact problems in layered elastic media. Beyond Markov matrices, some of the system matrix entries with row sum of one can be negative, which lead to signed Markov matrices. Physical insight behind the construction of these matrices and numerical examples will be presented.

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Explicit form of J.C.P. Miller formula and some applications

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We shall present an explicit form of the generalized J.C.P. Miller formula. The explicit form allows to apply the formula to compute coefficients of the composition $B_a \circ f$, where B_a is the binomial formal power series and f is a formal power series (possibly unit). We shall also show some applications of that form of the generalized J.C.P. Miller formula.

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K -means clustering based maximal residual Kaczmarz methods for solving large scale system of linear equations

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In recent years, the Kaczmarz method has garnered significant attention for solving ultra-large-scale consistent linear systems due to its minimal storage requirements. To effectively enhance the efficiency of the Kaczmarz method, we employ k -means clustering method based on cosine distance to partition all equations (or equivalently, hyperplanes) into k clusters. Subsequently, in each iteration, the approximate solution is updated using the equation with the maximum residual within a randomly selected cluster, thereby constructing a k -means clustering based randomized maximum residual Kaczmarz (abbreviated as RMRK(k)) method. To further enhance the computational efficiency, a maximum residual block Kaczmarz method with k -means clustering (abbreviated as MRBK(k)) is constructed by simultaneously updating the approximate solution using the equations with the maximum residuals within each cluster. The convergence of both methods is rigorously proved, demonstrating that for any chosen initial value in the column space of coefficient matrix, the iterative sequences generated by both methods converge to the minimum-norm solution of the linear system. Numerical experimental results validate the feasibility and effectiveness of these two methods.

A New Combination of Vector Extrapolation Methods and Multigrid Solvers For Isogeometric Analysis Applied To Linear and Nonlinear Problems

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In this work, we introduce a new approach for efficiently solving large, sparse linear systems arising from the discretization of elliptic partial differential equations using isogeometric analysis. Our method integrates vector extrapolation techniques with geometric multigrid solvers, significantly enhancing the performance of standard multigrid iterations with classical smoothers. We further extend this approach to nonlinear problems by employing polynomial-type extrapolation methods to improve the convergence of fixed-point methods such as the Picard iterative method. This work provides quadratic convergence results for polynomial extrapolation methods. Specifically, a new theoretical result on the correlation between the residual norm and the error norm, as well as a new estimation for the generalized residual norm of some extrapolation methods, are given. Through various numerical experiments, we demonstrate that the proposed combination of multigrid solvers with polynomial extrapolation methods significantly accelerates convergence and provides a robust alternative to existing techniques, such as Anderson acceleration.

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Projection on the intersection of convex sets

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In this talk we shall present a solution of the problem of projecting a point onto the intersection of several closed convex sets in \mathbf{R}^n , when a projection on each individual convex set is known. We propose a highly parallelizable method. The key idea in our approach is the reformulation of the original problem as a system of semi-smooth equations, thus enabling a fast semi-smooth Newton iterative technique based on Clarke's generalized gradients. Our algorithm has a form of an almost decentralized solution method. These features make the overall method attractive for distributed computing platforms, e.g. sensor networks.

Direct link between bounded rank perturbation problem and matrix pencil completion problem

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In this talk we shall present recently discovered direct link between two classical Linear Algebra problems. One is the bounded rank perturbation problem and the other one is the matrix pencil completion problem. Both of them are well studied separately. We present a novel, unexpected, direct link between them. In addition, we show how to use this link to obtain a solution to bounded rank perturbation problem via completion of pencils in concrete cases.

θ -subspace algorithms for detecting large definite matrix pairs

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For two Hermitian matrices A, B of the same order, the matrix pair (A, B) is called definite if there exists a real parameter θ such that the matrix $H(\theta) = \cos \theta A + \sin \theta B$ is positive definite. If a Hermitian matrix pair is not definite, we call it indefinite. Let (A, B) be a given Hermitian matrix pair whose definiteness is not known in advance. If A or B is a definite matrix, then the pair (A, B) is trivially definite. But, when both matrices are indefinite, it is not trivial to determine whether the pair is definite or not. This problem becomes especially challenging when dealing with large matrices. We propose a basic θ -subspace algorithm for detecting large definite matrix pairs. This algorithm finds one parameter θ if the given pair is definite, or declares that the pair is indefinite. The algorithm has three criteria to confirm the indefiniteness. By combining some existing algorithms for computing the Crawford number [2] and our basic algorithm, we get specialized algorithms for detecting definiteness of large matrix pairs. These algorithms can be applied to matrix pairs (A, B) in which matrices are too large to fit whole in the memory or are given only implicitly through procedures $x \mapsto Ax$ and $x \mapsto Bx$ for a given vector x .

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Stability and Perturbation Bounds for Gyroscopic Systems

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In this talk, we will consider a linear gyroscopic mechanical systems of the form

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + G\dot{x}(t) + Kx(t) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where the mass matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and the stiffness matrix $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are symmetric positive definite matrices, while the gyroscopic matrix $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is skew-symmetric, and $x = x(t)$ is a time-dependent displacement vector. The properties of the system (1) are defined by those of the associated quadratic eigenvalue problem (QEP)

$$\mathcal{G}(\lambda)x = (\lambda^2 M + \lambda G + K)x = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{C}^n, \quad x \neq 0. \quad (2)$$

We will provide an overview of various linearizations and transformations of the QEP (2) that can be used to develop efficient numerical methods for applications such as the stability analysis of gyroscopic systems and perturbation theory. Example of obtained results are relative perturbation bounds for the eigenvalues as well as the sin Θ -type bound for the perturbation of the corresponding eigenspaces for different types of stable gyroscopic systems.

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Numerically stable evaluation of closed-form expressions for eigenvalues of 3x3 matrices

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Standard (non-iterative) closed-form expressions for eigenvalues of 3x3 matrices are based on the roots of their characteristic polynomial. These are not forward stable due to the ill-conditioning of the roots in the vicinity of higher multiplicity. Nevertheless, the eigenvalues are well-conditioned functions of the matrix entries, as follows from the Bauer-Fike theorem [2]. In this work, we take the perspective of avoiding the intermediate step of computing the characteristic polynomial and principal matrix invariants. Instead, we focus on a set of more suitable matrix invariants. The core idea is based on the use of matrix discriminant expansion from [1]. We show that for symmetric matrices, this expansion leads to a sum-of-squares formula for the matrix discriminant that is evaluated in a forward stable algorithm. This provides an alternative non-iterative algorithm for matrix eigenvalues with a forward error at the order of machine precision for the limit case of matrices with an eigenvalue of multiplicity two. Furthermore, we generalize the observations to all real-valued diagonalizable 3x3 matrices. In that case, we present a sum-of-products approach for the matrix discriminant and demonstrate the expected backward stability of the algorithm.

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Improving bounds for eigenvalues

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In this study, we introduce new eigenvalue inclusion regions for complex matrices, which enhance and extend well-known bounds, such as Gershgorin disks, Cassini ovals, and generalized Brauer regions [5,6,7,8,13]. Using refined quantities such as the sums of deleted absolute rows, we derive sharper and more accurate localization sets for eigenvalues based on the alternative Brauer set formulated by Melman [1,9,10]. These new regions provide tighter bounds on the eigenvalues, thereby improving the precision of spectral analysis [2,3,4]. Furthermore, we explore the implications of these new bounds in providing sufficient conditions for the nonsingularity of matrices, which are crucial for ensuring system stability. In addition, they are applied to computing sharper bounds on the moduli of polynomial zeros and compared by the constructed sets in [11,12]. Our theoretical findings are supported by a series of numerical examples that illustrate the efficiency and effectiveness of the new inclusion regions compared to existing methods.

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A restarted Krylov method for small eigenvalues

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In this talk we present a new type of Restarted Krylov method for calculating the k smallest eigenvalues of a large sparse symmetric positive definite matrix, G . The new framework avoids the Lanczos tridiagonalization process, and the use of polynomial filtering. This simplifies the restarting mechanism and allows the introduction of several modifications. Convergence is assured by a monotonicity property that pushes the eigenvalues toward their limits. An important advantage of the new scheme is the freedom that we have in the choice of a matrix that generates the Krylov subspace. Thus, when looking for the smallest eigenvalues the subspace is generated by a matrix that approximates G^{-1} . In practice the matrix-vector product $G^{-1}\mathbf{b}$ is approximated by applying an iterative (or direct) method for solving the linear system $G\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$, and there is no need in exact solution. However, in some cases computing an approximate solution is too expensive. In such cases G is replaced by $\alpha I - G$ where α estimates the largest eigenvalue of G . Numerical experiments illustrate the usefulness of the proposed approach.

Recent advances on inner-product free Krylov methods

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Inverse problems – or the reconstruction of hidden objects or parameters from possibly noisy indirect measurements – naturally appear in a wide variety of applications, e.g. in medicine (computed tomography, CT), industry (non-destructive testing) and science (geophysics). However, these problems can be of very large-scale and the reconstructions are typically very sensitive to perturbations in the measurements. Using Krylov subspace methods is a very natural choice of solver for these problems, since they are efficient; matrix-free, and have regularizing properties.

Moreover, the development and commercialization of modern computer architectures, has sparked a renewed interest in methods exploiting low precision arithmetic and parallelization. In this case, avoiding inner products might be beneficial since they can cause undesired early stopping of the algorithms due to reorthogonalizing causing a significant loss of information in low precision; and require global communication. In particular, I will revise two solvers based on the Hessenberg method: the changing minimal residual Hessenberg method (CMRH) and the least-squares LU method (LSLU); and show the most recent advances in this area for linear discrete inverse problems.

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Randomized algorithms for coupled decompositions

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Coupled decompositions are a widely used tool for data fusion. In this talk we are going to discuss the coupled matrix factorization (CMF) where two matrices X and Y are represented in a low-rank format sharing one common factor, as well as the coupled matrix and tensor factorization (CMTF) where a matrix Y and a tensor X are represented in a low-rank format sharing a factor matrix. In order to speed up computation process, we explore several randomization techniques. The first one is an adaptation of the broadly used randomized SVD [2] to the case of coupled factorizations. Further on, we study randomized subspace iteration [2,3] and randomized block Krylov iteration [3] for the case of coupled decompositions. We are going to present the results of our extensive numerical tests. Furthermore, as a novel approach and with a high success rate, we apply our randomized algorithms to the face recognition problem. This talk is based on the preprint [1].

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Damping optimization of mechanical systems – rod/string model

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In this talk, we investigate two optimization criteria for damping optimization in a multi-body oscillator system with arbitrary degrees of freedom (n), resembling string/rod free vibrations. The first criterion is total average energy over all possible initial data and the second is the total average displacement over all possible initial data. Our first result shows that both criteria are equivalent to the trace minimization of the solution of the Lyapunov equation with different right-hand sides. As the second result we proved that in the case of damping with one damper, the minimal trace for each criterion can be expressed as a simple (linear or cubic) function of dimension n . Consequently, the optimal damping position is determined solely by the number of dominant eigenfrequencies and the optimal viscosity, independent of dimension n , offering a simplified approach to damping optimization in such systems. The presented theoretical framework and results will be illustrated with numerical examples.

Solving a Class of Fractional Differential Equation Using the Matrix Mittag-Leffler Function

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Many anomalous diffusion problems can be modeled using a time-dependent fractional diffusion equation (FDE). Originally derived within the framework of continuous-time random walks with heavy-tailed waiting time distributions, these equations have since become a standard approach for describing subdiffusive dynamics. To obtain approximate solutions for such FDEs, one can discretize the spatial operator, reducing the problem to a semi-linear fractional-time equation, whose solution can be expressed in closed form using the Mittag-Leffler (ML) function with a matrix argument, multiplied by a vector.

Due to recent advancements in the numerical computation of matrix ML functions [1, 2, 3], this tool can now be used to develop robust ML integrators for solving the underlying semi-linear fractional-time equations. In this presentation, we investigate which ML integrators are the most suitable for solving the aforementioned FDEs. Several numerical examples are presented to illustrate the performance of these integrators, highlighting their strengths and limitations.

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Quadratures with quasi-degree of exactness

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Monic orthogonal polynomials satisfy a three-term recurrence relation whose coefficients determine a symmetric tridiagonal Jacobi matrix. To efficiently compute the nodes and weights of Gauss quadrature, the Golub-Welsch algorithm, based on the observations that the nodes are the eigenvalues of the Jacobi matrix and that the weights are proportional to the square of the first components of corresponding normalized eigenvectors, can be applied. The Gauss quadrature with n nodes is exact for all polynomials of degree $\leq 2n - 1$ and represents a unique optimal interpolatory quadrature rule. After choosing m arbitrary points x_k (at which the integrand is defined), we transform the given integral into a sum of an integral that does not cause a quadrature error and an integral with a property that the points x_k are the zeros of its modified integrand. Then, we approximate the integral of the modified integrand by an n -point quadrature \mathcal{G}_n whose nodes and weights are simply expressed in terms of the nodes and weights of associated n -point Gauss quadrature. Formula \mathcal{G}_n is exact for all polynomials of degree $\leq 2n - 1 + m$ with m fixed zeros x_k , but those fixed zeros should not be a disadvantage, since the modified integrand has the same zeros.

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Trace maximization algorithm for the approximate tensor diagonalization

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Tensors are a generalization to scalars, vectors and matrices. The order of a tensor is defined by the number of directions, called modes, that is required to describe it. E.g. matrix is a 2nd order and vector is a 1st order tensor. In this talk we speak about a Jacobi-type algorithm for the approximate diagonalization of tensors of order greater than 2 via tensor trace maximization. For a general tensor this is an alternating least squares algorithm and the rotation matrices are chosen in each mode one-by-one to maximize the tensor trace. Unlike matrices, not every symmetric tensor can be diagonalized. For symmetric tensors we discuss a structure-preserving variant of the algorithm where in each iteration the same rotation is applied in all modes. We show that both versions of the algorithm converge to the stationary points of the corresponding objective functions.

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Tensor Means under Tensor-Tensor Products with Invertible Linear Transforms

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While matrix means, such as the geometric mean and the Wasserstein mean of positive-definite matrices, have been widely researched, their extension to tensors remains relatively unexplored. Understanding tensor means can lead to advancements in tasks such as tensor-based data clustering and improved modeling of higher-order relationships in scientific and engineering domains. The goal of this presentation is to introduce two tensor means for third-order tensors, extendable to higher-order tensors, under the tensor-tensor product with an arbitrary invertible linear transform. We remark that this product is a generalized notion of the T-product. First, we define positive definiteness, eigendecomposition and trace of third-order tensors under this tensor-tensor product. Secondly, we generalize the concept of geometric mean to tensors that are positive-definite under the tensor-tensor product and show that this geometric mean satisfies certain properties which a “mean” should satisfy. We then show that the geometric mean is a unique positive-definite solution of a specific algebraic Riccati tensor equation and that it is the midpoint of a geodesic on the manifold of positive-definite tensors for a specific Riemannian metric. Lastly, after changing the Riemannian metric on the manifold, we also define the concept of Wasserstein mean of two tensors under this same product.

Perfect properties of the ranks of some tensors

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Tensors are higher-dimensional generalisations of matrices, and likewise the notion of rank on matrices can be extended to ranks on tensors. There are several competing generalisations of matrix rank, and the most suitable notion usually depends on the context. The oldest of these notions is arguably the tensor rank, but recently some other notions arose, such as the slice rank, partition rank, and geometric rank. Often, the immediate analogue for the ranks of tensors of a basic “perfect” property that held for matrix rank is incorrect, and one direction that has been explored has been to show that these analogues may be corrected with neither a too major complication nor a major decrease in conceptual strength. After recalling several definitions of ranks on tensors, we will in this talk consider another way of transforming these immediate analogues into valuable and correct statements: rather than show that some inevitably weaker property holds for all tensors, we can show that the “perfect” property does hold in its original formulation for some tensors - those that do not involve the phenomena involved in the counterexamples motivating the other line of thought - rather than for all tensors. This class of tensors can be concisely described.

ML&NC Workshop

Plenary lectures

Linear Operators Learning for Dynamical Systems

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This talk presents a framework to learn dynamical systems through the lens of linear evolution operators, in particular the semi-group of transfer operators and their infinitesimal generator. We review recent operator estimators, whose domain is either a reproducing kernel Hilbert space or the span of finitely many basis functions learned by a neural network. An important focus is to use the operators for forecasting future states of the system and explain system dynamics via the operators' spectra. We present statistical learning bounds for the operator estimators and their spectral decomposition, highlighting the important role of the learned representation and the estimator's rank. Applications to molecular dynamics and other dynamical systems will be discussed during the talk.

Molecular dynamics: the AI revolution

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In recent years the application of machine learning methodologies has led to major advances in molecular dynamics simulation. Nowadays simulations of unprecedented complexity and accuracy can be routinely performed. This newly acquired capability is having a major impact in several areas of science like material science, catalysis and biology. We shall review some of these progresses and illuminate a way forward in which rather than sampling individual configurations or single trajectories one evolves probability distribution.

Randomized algorithms in numerical linear algebra and the column subset selection problem

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Randomization is among the most exciting developments in numerical linear algebra (NLA), and has led to algorithms that are fast, scalable, robust, and reliable.

The column subset selection problem (CSSP) is simple to state but not easy to solve, and has far-reaching consequences in a number of applications in computational mathematics. Several randomized and deterministic algorithms are now available for the CSSP.

In this talk I will review a few prominent topics in randomized NLA (low-rank approximation, least-squares problems, norm/trace estimation). We will then explore the CSSP from computational and theoretical viewpoints, highlighting their power in practical applications.

Contributed talks

Parallel Compact PFFT-Type Algorithms in the Machine Learning Kernel Methods for 3D Scattering Problems

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In this talk, we present efficient parallel compact partial FFT algorithms in the implementation of the Gaussian Process (GP) regression-type kernel methods for prediction of the scattering signal at the nodes of a regular 2D rectangular grids based on the noisy nonregular training data set on a given surface generated by the 3D Helmholtz solver representing the subsurface scattering model. The solution of the 3D Helmholtz equation is based on the combination of GMRES-PFFT algorithms proposed in our previous publications. The uncertainty-quantification (UQ) parameters at each point in the test set are the primary targets of the proposed learning methods.

The proposed algorithms significantly increase the efficiency of the considered supervised learning problem. The complexity analysis of the proposed PFFT algorithms is considered. The efficiency of the proposed method is compared with the standard Cholesky factorization method commonly used in this problem. The parallel variants of the developed algorithms are implemented in OpenMP and MPI C- extension.

The complexity and scalability of the methods are analyzed on subsurface scattering problems with realistic ranges of parameters in soil and mine-like targets.

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On the convergence of denoiser-driven image reconstruction

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Over the past decade, researchers have developed state-of-the-art iterative algorithms that apply image denoisers as regularizers for reconstruction tasks like compressed sensing, deblurring, and superresolution. However, the unpredictable behavior of these denoisers can introduce instability into the reconstruction process. Providing theoretical guarantees is particularly challenging, as existing analyses often rely on strong assumptions that are difficult to validate in practical scenarios. In this talk, we will focus on a class of linear (but data-driven) denoisers called kernel denoisers that are highly effective for denoiser-driven reconstruction. From a mathematical perspective, kernel denoisers come with a tractable formulation and can be represented as positive semidefinite linear operators with spectra in $[0,1]$. Using these and other spectral properties, we can establish linear (geometric) convergence of the iterative process for a broad class of linear inverse problems and, importantly, under verifiable assumptions. We will review these results in this talk, which were arrived at using a purely operator-theoretic approach via the contraction mapping theorem. We will then explain how a similar convergence guarantee can be arrived at by associating the iterative process with a strongly convex optimization problem and using the Polyak-Lojasiewicz (PL) inequality. We will also discuss challenges in extending the analysis to other reconstruction algorithms and trained denoisers.

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Joint Communication, Localization, Sensing, and Radio SLAM

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This paper introduces a groundbreaking framework to achieve sub-50 cm accuracy in communication, localization, sensing, and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [1]. It ensures seamless operation in indoor and outdoor environments by integrating 5G mmWave signals, GNSS, WiFi, and Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs). Applications span healthcare, intelligent transportation systems (ITS), extended reality (XR), cooperative robotics, automated systems, and micromobility solutions like e-scooters and bicycles for urban delivery.

The system leverages advanced deep learning (DL) algorithms and a self-supervised radio visual representation learning pipeline. By synchronizing radio and visual data, this method effectively overcomes the challenges posed by unlabeled data sets, allowing precise environmental mapping and recognition of human activity [2]. Reliance on mmWave communication ensures high-resolution data acquisition, with advanced signal processing techniques to extract channel state information (CSI) to enhance localization and environmental mapping [1].

The framework integrates Privacy-Preserving AI, a pivotal feature to ensure user confidentiality, addressing privacy concerns often linked to camera-based solutions where video footage constitutes personally identifiable information (PII). It bypasses the limitations of traditional camera and lidar systems, such as high costs, dependence on perfect visibility conditions, and constrained reliability in adverse weather. The framework also incorporates bioinspired strategies, taking cues from echolocation bats and dolphins that employ AoA and ToA mechanisms for spatial awareness. These biological principles improve multipath mitigation strategies and enable environmental mapping with reduced computational overhead, improving its resilience and adaptability in various scenarios. [3].

Recent advancements in linear algebra-driven machine learning algorithms, such as neural tangent kernels and matrix completion models, are used to enhance data-driven localization systems. These models enable precise analysis of multipath effects, Channel State Information (CSI), and Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) parameters. Furthermore, self-supervised learning methodologies inspired by the latest developments in radio-visual representation learning ensure adaptive performance in diverse scenarios.

The indoor implementation employs mmWave and WiFi-based SLAM [1], enabling dynamic localization and mapping of surroundings. The geometric connection between the propagation of the mmWave signal and the environment ensures reliable performance, even in scenarios with complex reflections. For outdoor

environments, GNSS and 5G hybrid models incorporate advanced error correction techniques, including Kalman filtering and real-time kinematic (RTK) enhancements, to achieve high accuracy in urban and GNSS-denied areas. The concept of Personal Radar [4], embedded in devices like smartphones and e-scooters, transforms them into active environmental sensors, leveraging mmWave arrays for beamforming and backscatter signal processing. This capability allows infrastructure-free mapping, ensuring resilience under low-visibility conditions.

This paper not only advances the scientific and technical state-of-the-art but also introduces impactful societal benefits. By supporting privacy-aware, energy-efficient, and scalable localization and mapping, it sets a foundation for safer micromobility systems, enhanced healthcare diagnostics, and more intuitive XR environments. Such precision, achieved through collaborative innovations, paves the way for groundbreaking applications in urban living and smart cities.

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Accelerated multiple row-and column-action methods and their convergence analyses

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For solving the large-scale linear system using iterative methods, we employ the Petrov-Galerkin conditions and an adaptive-momentum technique, and introduce two deterministic multiple row- and column-action methods. Our convergence analysis shows that these resulting algorithms possess linear convergence rates, bounded by the explicit expressions. Theoretically, we demonstrate that our proposed methods exhibit faster convergence rates compared to those without momentum acceleration, as seen in Chen and Huang (Numer. Algor., 2022, 89: 1007-1029; East Asian J. Appl. Math., 2022, 12: 406-420). We present several numerical experiments to substantiate our theoretical results and discuss real-world applications, such as data fitting in computeraided geometric design, for illustrative purposes.

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On A Deterministic Block Newton-Kaczmarz Method

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For solving large-scale system of nonlinear equations, a deterministic block Newton-Kaczmarz method based on a greedy strategy is proposed.

At each Newton step, a greedy Kaczmarz-type step is used to solve the linear system. It is deterministic, adaptive and needs not to compute the pseudoinverses of submatrices. The method will converge linearly to the nearest solution to the initial point under mild conditions, which contains the local tangent cone condition.

Numerical experiments are performed to illustrate that the method is efficient compared to four deterministic methods at least for the tested problems.

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Greedy Block Extended Kaczmarz Method for Solving the Least Squares Problems

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A greedy block extended Kaczmarz method is introduced for solving the least squares problem where the greedy rule combines the maximum-distances with relaxation parameters. In order to save the computational cost of MooreCPenrose inverse, an average projection technique is used. The convergence theory of the greedy block extended Kaczmarz method is established and an upper bound for the convergence rate is also derived. Numerical experiments show that the proposed method is efficient and better than the randomized block extended Kaczmarz methods in terms of the number of iteration steps and computational time.

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Numerical Linear algebra for Operator Learning: Challenges and Opportunities

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In this talk, I will discuss how numerical linear algebra can support the design of machine learning algorithms for learning linear operators from data, with a focus on both scalability and theoretical guarantees. I'll discuss problems such as learning Koopman operators or solving vector-valued regression tasks, where the objective is to recover an operator from high-dimensional or time-dependent data. Methods like kernel principal component regression or reduced-rank regression offer strong statistical properties but are often computationally demanding. I'll show how randomized sketching techniques can make these approaches scalable while preserving their theoretical guarantees. More broadly, the talk highlights how tools from numerical linear algebra play a central role in developing reliable and efficient algorithms for operator learning.

Convex Extension of the Kaczmarz Algorithm for Efficient Computation of Sparse Inverses of Positive Definite Matrices

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This talk presents a novel approach to computing sparse approximate inverse factors of symmetric positive definite (SPD) matrices using a convex extension of the Kaczmarz algorithm. We introduce both randomized and greedy Bregman projection algorithms that efficiently handle scenarios where only a limited number of matrix elements are known and treated as constraints. Our method guarantees numerical efficiency by implementing iteration steps that perform rank-one updates of Cholesky factors, significantly reducing computational costs. We establish linear convergence rates for our algorithms and demonstrate how dynamic shifting techniques can further accelerate convergence. The proposed approach is particularly valuable for large-scale sparse systems where traditional factorization methods become prohibitively expensive. Experimental results validate the effectiveness of our method across several test cases, showing its potential applications in preconditioning techniques for iterative solvers and sparse inverse covariance estimation problems.

Neural dynamics methods for solving system of matrix equations and applications to advanced data analytics

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We deal with several neural dynamics models for solving linear and non-linear matrix equations in a real time. The fundamental idea behind these models is to construct a dynamic system which state matrix converges to the desired solution. The convergence properties of the presented models are investigated in details using the Lyapunov method, showing in most cases the global convergence to the solution determined by the initial values choice. Several discretizations of the proposed dynamics are also considered and compared to the existing iterative methods.

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